

Opportunities to Use Innovations in Tourism

Polatov is the son of Ma'murjon Murodjon

TDIU "Tourism and hotel business" department foundation doctoral student

Abstract:

In our country, since 2016, special attention has been paid to the development of tourism and improvement of its infrastructure. The development of tourism as a strategically important sector of the economy has been started. The development of tourism infrastructure and the formation of its components were constantly monitored.

Keywords: Economy, international tourism, ecotourism, infrastructure, attraction of innovations, service, attractions.

Enter

As we aim to create and improve the tourism infrastructure, first of all we need to find answers to the questions of what is the infrastructure and what is included in it. Infrastructure (Latin "Infra" - under, below, "structure" - structure, location) is a combination of service structures or objects that ensure the operation of an industry or network and its components are connected to each other. Infrastructures take a number of forms depending on their purpose and tasks. Among these, we will focus more on economic infrastructure based on the purpose. Economic infrastructure includes transport, communication, education and communal economy, housing, lifestyle training, and meeting the needs of the population for living together. If we take a broader approach, economic infrastructure is economic and cultural objects necessary for the population to live, forming its service networks (roads, canals, warehouses, transport, communication, energy, water and supply, science, education, healthcare, financial organizations, etc.) is considered a local administrative complex. Judging from the above, tourism infrastructure includes two main parts that are integral to the field.

The first major part is the hotels, accommodation facilities and organizations that provide restaurant and catering services that make up the tourism industry.

The second main part is the components that make up the infrastructure and includes three systems. The first system of infrastructure includes energy, communal services, finance, insurance,

communication, security systems that are not directly related to the production of tourist products, but are necessary for the provision of tourist services.

Tourist facilities, car rental, taxi fleets, cinemas, museums, exhibition halls, sports clubs, parks, zoos, etc., which directly serve the second and third part of the infrastructure for the production of tourism products. Includes service organizations.

Tourism infrastructure includes accommodation facilities (hotels, guesthouses, hostels, camping sites, motels), catering establishments (cafes, bars, restaurants), transport network (highways, railways, airports, ports, etc.), communication networks (electricity, wastewater, communication departments), law enforcement organizations, medical and household service organizations, gift shops, sports facilities and is closely connected with tourist service enterprises maybe

Tourism infrastructure is aimed at ensuring the necessary conditions for the provision of tourist services, the safety and health of tourists. We all know that tourists prefer to go to the region where the conditions for travel are created (peace, tranquility). The reason is that a tourist should feel safe wherever he is in a bus, train, hotel, or restaurant during his trip.

Literature analysis and methodology

S.S. Gulomov, K.Kh. Abdurahmanov, N.T. Tokhliyev, M.Q. Pardayev, A.A. Eshtayev, A.M. Abduvohidov, M.T. Aliyeva, A.N. Norchayev, D.Kh. Aslanova, B.N. Navroz-zoda, O.M. Pardayev, B.H. Torayev, O.H. Khamidov, B.Sh. Safarov, N.S. Ibragimov, S.S. Roziyev in the scientific works of tourism effective management of infrastructure development, rational use of tourist resources, problems in the development of the sector and the development of regional tourism.

The scientific works of the above-mentioned scientists and researchers contributed enough to the organization of tourist trips, the development of services at a high level, the effective use of resources, the introduction of modern management in the field and the improvement of infrastructure. Also, due to the fact that issues such as the effective use of innovative technologies in the development of tourism infrastructure, ensuring the employment of the local population through the development of regional tourism, development of the industry based on public-private partnership, and coordination of inter-sectoral activities have not been sufficiently studied in the scientific research conducted by them, they have introduced innovations in the revitalization of the tourism infrastructure. it is urgent to study the factors related to the mechanisms.

Analysis and results

Despite the fact that today in the global market products and services are produced according to the wishes of customers, the starting point in tourism is always approached based on the possibilities of providing products and services. However, the wide use of innovations in the improvement of products and services is aimed. When we hear the word innovation, we first think of new ideas, new technologies, discoveries in production, sustainable development, infrastructure, increasing labor productivity, scientific achievements, modernization of production, new design developments, new service provision, comes such as a change of worldview. Based on this, if we assume that tourism consists mainly of service processes, even if this field has financial and administrative influence, it will be very difficult to implement technological changes. It has always been difficult to attract the technologies and leading experts necessary for tourism. Questions arise as to which sectors of tourism can implement innovations, what should be taken into account when implementing them. Innovations in tourism can be implemented on the basis of the following principles:

- scope of coverage. Innovation can be introduced at the scale of all sectors of tourism, specially designated enterprises, region, country, territory, city, development of new tourist products or modernization of existing ones, specific tourist object;

- launch. Information platforms for tourists, management of employees, opening of new jobs, hotel reservations, implementation of microcredits in the opening of private guest houses, technical support of the service industry, online registration at the airport.
- speed of application. Depending on the purpose of each country, strategic innovations are implemented gradually, from the point of view of scarcity (transport, communication), the introduction of reactive innovations requires rapid implementation in the short term. This mainly takes into account political realities and the behavior of competitors in the market (visa policy).

In the introduction of innovations to the tourism infrastructure, it is necessary to approach based on natural geographical factors, weather conditions and historical and cultural heritage. Developing new products and services by directing them correctly will increase the potential of the development of the industry.

In the application of innovations for the development of tourism infrastructure, processes requiring the implementation of large-scale projects and complex technologies have also been observed, which can be taken as an example of the mountain ski track established in the "Emirates Mall" in Dubai, UAE. This major project was carried out in a consistent manner, probably to boost the spirits of tourists and locals alike. Apart from some major infrastructure projects like this one, tourism relies heavily on small businesses.

For example, Uzbekistan is a country with a wonderful climate, beautiful nature, and rich history, rather than its location. At the same time, it is located at the intersection of the "Great Silk Road". Such opportunities give rise to the notion that even if tourism does not introduce innovative technologies, it will maintain competitiveness. For example, Egyptian Arab Ehrams in the republic attract millions of tourists from all over the world. The coasts of Egypt are washed by the waters of the Red and Mediterranean seas, and tourists who use these opportunities can divide their vacation into two parts. These are historical-adventure travel and beach recreation. The organization of such trips is widely implemented in Greece, Turkey, India, Thailand, Spain, Vietnam, and Israel.

In countries similar to our republic, that is, without direct access to the sea, opportunities to improve tourism infrastructure, organize services and use innovations to attract more tourists requires competition with relatively high countries.

Taking into account the above, we need to know the sequence of stages of innovation application and implementation. For this, it is necessary to master the following:

- in terms of the scope of innovations, the entire industry, individual enterprise, country, city, creation of new tourist products or improvement of existing ones, introduction on the scale of tourist objects;
- in the introduction of innovations, it is necessary to use them widely, especially in the platforms that help in the search of tourists, in the management of service personnel and their employment. At the same time, opening catering enterprises, transport organizations, hotels, guesthouses, providing technical services (for example, online registration at the airport) through mechanisms supported by subsidies, microcredits and public-private partnerships;
- speed of introduction of innovations. In this case, strategic innovations are gradually implemented in each sector (transport communications). On the contrary, the introduction of reactive innovations (visa cancellation for a country that wants to attract more tourists) is accelerating.

At the same time, innovation implementation processes are gradual and require great care. Because if the funds spent on innovation are implemented incorrectly at any stage, all the actions taken can be canceled.

At the first stage, it is necessary to bring the ideas into one system. In this, internal opportunities for the practical application of the new ideas that have arisen are identified. A number of alternatives of new ideas may appear, and among them, those considered to have a future are selected. It is determined that the selected idea corresponds to the market image and development strategy of the tourist company, and the implementation of the future new service is determined.

In the second stage, information on changes in the market will begin to be collected in order to implement the identified idea. The collected information is analyzed and the potential, opportunities and risk level of the tourist company and its standards are determined for the implementation of the service that is expected to be offered to the market.

In the third stage, the economic efficiency of new services is analyzed, and its marketing costs and programs are developed. At the same time, when the idea turns into a concrete project, the position of the tourist market, supply and demand, consumption characteristics are very important. In this case, it is necessary to calculate the costs of creating and developing new services, to make sure of the availability of resources, to identify financial sources, and to evaluate the potential of personnel. After that, the terms of development of new services, assessment of its profitability and its presentation to the market are carried out.

In the fourth stage, the previous three stages are implemented. It is clear from this that the implementation of innovations in tourism companies is a complex process. In the fourth stage, the following are mainly carried out along with the above:

- a specific program for the distribution of work between the company's departments and the creation of a new service will be developed;
- conducting research on environmental, safety and other indicators for the type of service created;
- service type naming, trademark determination and new approaches are implemented.

In the fifth stage, a direct market test will be conducted. At the same time, tests will be conducted on the provision of price and price discounts, and the granting of loans for at least three months. At the same time, the selection of advertising types and implementation methods, implementation of measures in unexpected situations are checked.

At the sixth stage, a decision is made to enter the created service type into the market, and the new service type is introduced. In this, the volume of services provided, profitability, level of satisfaction of demands and needs, methods of service are constantly monitored. In addition:

- taking over the market, reputation of the tourist company, constant relations with customers;
- effective use of available opportunities, conclusion of contracts with qualified employees;
- finding financial resources and attracting investments for the development of a new type of service on a large scale;
- adaptation of the new type of service to international standards, patenting works are carried out.

If all of the factors considered above are successfully implemented, any tourism company that introduces innovations in its activities will capture the market and achieve maximum profit. As a result, a tourist company can gain a monopoly position in the market.

Figure 1. Stages of the innovation implementation process.

Our research shows that it is necessary to learn how and where to apply innovations. There should always be innovations in solving problems that arise everywhere. Demand for tourist services creates supply. Tourists become direct consumers without participating in the creation of new services. When applying innovations in tourism, marketers constantly study the segment of tourists and what they are interested in, as well as determine what they want. Such information will serve to find which services are in high demand in the tourist market and find innovative solutions to meet the demand. For example, in the countries of Western Europe, North America and South-East Asia, where ecotourism has developed, innovations are widely used to create maximum conditions for tourists in guest houses or families in the countryside. Similarly, guest house owners are creating all the conditions to receive tourists.

Another area where innovations are widely used in tourism is museums. Virtual services are widely introduced in museums. Tourists are given the opportunity to travel to famous museums, see unique exhibits, and tour the entire museum through the Internet. In this case, tourists can walk through its halls, get information about the exhibits, and conduct research without coming to the museum. Due to the widespread introduction of innovations in this field, visiting museums is becoming increasingly popular among tourists. For example, the world-famous Louvre Museum opened its doors to the public for the first time on November 8, 1793, and today receives more than 10 million visitors a year. Every year "The Art Newspaper" publishes the list of the most visited museums in the world. Currently, there are 60-80 such millionaire museums operating in the world. According to the list compiled by "The Art Newspaper" the National Museum of China (Beijing) 7,390,000, the Vatican Museum (Vatican) 6,882,931, the Metropolitan Museum of Art (New York) 6,479,548, the British Museum (London) 6,239,983, Tate Modern Museum (London) 6,098,340, National Gallery (London) 6,011,007, State Hermitage Museum (St. Petersburg) 4,956,529, Museo Reina Sofía Museum (Madrid) 4,425,699, National Art Gallery (Washington) served 4,074,403 visitors. In order to overcome the competition between these museums, the demand for innovative technologies is increasing. If we look at the historical development of the tourism infrastructure, after the introduction of innovations (after the 70s of the last century), unprecedented achievements have been made. Despite the changes in technology, the tourism infrastructure is developing on the basis

of innovation. Compared to previous technological changes, tourism is currently ahead of other industries in the use of new technologies.

Conclusions and suggestions.

If we analyze in conclusion, first of all, scientific-technological innovations, taken as the main factor, changed the living conditions of people and the nature of production. Innovations have also reshaped production and become its main driving force. The innovative development of science and technology has significantly increased labor productivity, and through the improvement of social protection, per capita income has increased significantly, as a result, new forms of tourism activity have emerged.

Secondly, the introduction of scientific and technological innovations leads to more free time for the population. Having more free time is one of the important conditions of recreational tourism. With the development of science and technology, the automation of management and production has significantly increased labor productivity. As a result, people's demand for leisure and vacation travel increased as average working hours decreased significantly.

Thirdly, scientific and technological innovations are also strengthening tourism activities. In the last 20 years, due to the improvement of people's literacy, education level and life activities, some tourists are more interested in learning scientific and technological innovations during the trip along with the enjoyment of travel.

The introduction of scientific and technological innovations has created high demands in the implementation of modern tourism. Such factors force us to look for new types of tourism, unlike traditional tourism, through the use of information processing, development of social networks, as well as support for tourists visiting in scientific direction and the use of new technologies.

We can see that the use of scientific and technological innovations improves the quality of tourist services in the following ways:

First, scientific and technological innovations increase the variety of tourism products and extend their life cycle. Tourism in improving the effective delivery of tourist products to customers and constantly updating the services provided industry widely uses innovative technologies. Investments in the introduction of innovative technologies also help to extend the life cycle of tourism products. If we take Disneyland as an example, the entertainment centers built as a result of investing in the use of new technologies while absorbing the achievements of science attract tourists from all over the world.

If we consider the impact of scientific and technological innovations on the development of tourism infrastructure, firstly, scientific and technological innovations are of great importance in the transport infrastructure. The rapid development of large highways, local highways, high-speed trains, and civil aviation has accelerated the movement of tourists several times and increased the safety of movement. At the same time, the improvement of the means of transport and the use of new technologies led to a significant improvement in the service to tourists. The increase in the number of private cars, the creation of car rental opportunities is another convenience for tourists. For example, if we talk about the possibilities offered by the Alipay and UnionPay payment systems, it will greatly help to eliminate queues and traffic jams, as well as save tourists' time by making electronic payment for parking a private car. At the same time, it offers convenience such as the function of searching for the tourist bus stop and the use of various maps and navigation programs. In addition, with the application of innovative technology to tourism, tourists are provided with a number of conveniences such as electronic travel code, electronic ticket, electronic registration, issuance of permits through electronic facial recognition.

Secondly, innovations also influenced the development of the infrastructure of information and communication technologies. As a result of the improvement of modern communication technologies, it was possible to provide tourists with quality communication during the entire trip. Through IoT programs, tourists have the opportunity to receive all kinds of information about the address of tourist objects, route scheme using mobile phones, personal computers and other platform devices at any time. For example, "Virgin" hotel has achieved a 266% increase in hotel orders due to the active use of innovative information and communication technologies.

Thirdly, scientific and innovative technological innovations are improving the management of tourism infrastructure. In this, first of all, scientific and technological innovations are of great importance in the protection and preservation of tourist resources. Digitization of classification and identification of tourist resources (cultural-historical, recreational, ecological), purchase and management of consumption is being carried out rapidly. Based on new technologies, it helps to store various information about tourism, sort resources, manage and analyze reports effectively. For example, one of the countries whose tourism is developing rapidly in recent years, the Chinese Academy "Dunhuang Academy" uses photographic image acquisition and processing, virtual travel, digital video, multimedia display, and three-dimensional technologies to create unique digital files of each historical object and museum exhibits. by creating permanent access opportunities for tourists.

Second, scientific and technological innovations help to manage tourism when emergency or unexpected situations arise. The use of innovative technologies facilitates the management of safety and emergency situations on tourist routes and ensures speedy resolution.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar va internet resurslari

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-son “O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivoj- lantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 07-fevraldagi PQ-3514-son qarori “O‘zbekiston bo‘ylab sayyohat qil!” ichki turizmni rivojlantirish dasturi.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prizidentining 2022-yil 30-apreldagi PQ-232-son qarori.
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022-yil 30-apreldagi PQ-232-son “Ichki turizm xizmatlarini diversifikatsiya qilishga oid qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida”gi qarori, <https://www.unwto.org/sustainable-development>.
5. B. R. Dehqonov. “Ichki turizmni ta’riflashda bo‘lgan qarashlar va turizm shakllarini o‘z ichiga olgan bog‘liqliklar” Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi: ilmiy jurnal. – №4-1 (88). – Xorazm Ma’mun akademiyasi, 2022 y. –81 b.
6. Rustamovich, Dehkonov Burhon. “Analysis of the Development of Tourism in Uzbekistan.”Journal of International Busi- ness Research and Marketing 5.6 (2020): 28-33.
7. Norchayev, A. N. “Turizm infratuzilmasida kutilayotgan o‘zgarishlar va imkoniyatlar. “Iqtisodiyot va innovatsion tex- nologiyalar” ilmiy elektron jurnali (2019).
8. Aliyeva, M. T. “Xo‘jayev O‘. X., Norchayev AN Turizm rivojlanishini prognozlash. O‘quv qo‘llanma.” –T.: TDIU. –214 (2006).